

The Importance Role of Human Capital of Independent Commissioner on the Credit Performance of Indonesian Rural Bank

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Financial Performance, Internal Governance, Independent Commissioner, Human Capital, Education, Indonesian Rural Bank</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5140342</p>	<p><i>Purpose: This study aims to test the effect of independent commissioner's existence on credit performance by examining the moderating role of the human capital of independent commissioners. Design/methodology/approach: Using purposive sampling, 177 rural banks in Indonesia become the study sample and multiple-step linear regression to analyze it. Findings: The human capital of an independent commissioner moderate the effect of the independent commissioner's existence on the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. Originality/value: This research hopefully will give empirical evidence and comprehensive understanding to the academicians, public researchers, and the authority that independent commissioner's existence as a critical factor of Indonesian Rural Bank's internal governance mechanism. Its' education suitability should support to ensure it can effectively implement the governance.</i></p>

Introduction

The Indonesian Government through Bank Indonesia (BI) as the Indonesian Central Bank, has encouraged the role of Indonesian Rural Banks in the development of SMEs by either appointing Indonesian Rural Banks - as executing agents or channeling agents in the linkage programs with the commercial banks - to extend credit to SMEs (BI, 2012).

According to OJK's (Indonesian Financial Services Authority) data in 2016, the growth rate of Indonesian Rural Banks' assets from 2011 to 2015 is increased by 16% (OJK, 2016), and credit disbursement reached IDR 79 billion.

Although the Indonesian Rural Bank's growth rate is outstanding, mostly 1,184 (68%) have limited core capital (CC) of less than IDR 6 billion. The main problem with Indonesian Rural Banks with core capital below IDR 6 billion is the financial performance of those rural banks tends to deteriorate. In the OJK's investigation, those worsening were caused by the lack of capital, the lack of management, the lack of governance, and the lack of the IT system (OJK, 2016).

As mention before, the deteriorating financial performance of rural banks has been pointed out by OJK (2016) that one of the main causes is weak governance implementation. The OJK allegation is in line with previous research, which states that their governance influences the financial performance of banks and other financial institutions (Handley-Schachler, Juleff, & Paton, 2007; Mersland & Strøm, 2009; Orazalin & Mahmood, 2019; Ross & Crossan, 2012; Zagorchev & Gao, 2015). Because of the importance of governance in the Indonesian Rural Bank and to ensure that its implementation has been carried out properly, OJK issued POJK No.4 / POJK.03 / 2015 concerning the Implementation of Governance for Indonesian Rural Banks. The regulations in the POJK came into force when the POJK was promulgated, namely on April 1, 2015.

Contrary to what has been regulated by the OJK through POJK No.4 / POJK.03 / 2015, the problem of deteriorating financial performance and poor financial performance occurs in BPRs with core capital below IDR 6 billion (OJK, 2016). In fact, according to OJK data (2016), there were 6 BPRs liquidated in 2014, 3 BPRs in 2015, and in 2016 (as of August 2016), 7 BPRs had core capital of less than IDR 3 billion. Meanwhile, according to Regulation No.4 / POJK.03 / 2015, only Indonesian Rural Banks with core capital of at least IDR 50 billion are required to have independent commissioners. In addition, the average BPR with problems is a BPR that has a shortage of management, in this case, a lack of directors and commissioners.

This research is concentrated to empirically analyze against the worsening cause of the lack of governance, mainly focused on the effects of independent commissioner factors in the effectiveness of Indonesian Rural Bank corporate governance implementation. According to OJK in POJK

No.4/POJK.03/2015, as mentioned before, the existence of an independent commissioner is only compulsory for Indonesian Rural Banks with core capital IDR 50 billion and above. In fact, contradictory with it, the worsening of financial performance precisely happened mostly in Indonesian Rural Banks with limited core capital (CC) of even less than IDR 6 billion.

Independent commissioners have a significant positive relationship with ROA and company stock returns in general (Rostami, Rostami, & Kohansal, 2015). These results are supported by (Nisasmara & Musdholifah, 2016) findings for the other financial performances but contradictory (Novia & Lukviarman, 2006; Zabri, Ahmad, & Wah, 2015). In other studies (Agrawal & Knoeber, 1996; Bhagat & Black, 2001; Drakos & Bekiris, 2010; Klein, 1998; Yermack, 1996), the results show that there is no significant relationship between the existence of independent commissioners and company performance. According to recent research, a higher size and ratio of independent commissioners does not always help bank performance (Lin & Chang, 2016). In other words, the results of studies on the effect of independent commissioners on company financial performance are still contradictory and inconsistent. Meanwhile, in terms of credit performance as the leading service in the banking sector, the independent commissioner at the Indonesian Rural Bank has a positive relationship with its credit performance (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018).

The mixed findings suggest further research is needed. Previous studies have not considered corporate governance's mediating and moderating effect (Hsu, Wang, Tsai, & Lu, 2012). Most of the research investigates how corporate governance and company performance are direct without moderator and mediator.

Relating to the Indonesian Rural Bank independent commissioner factors, Independent Commissioner Education decreases the Non-Performing Loan (increase credit performance) (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). These results support previous studies of (Bonner & Lewis, 1990), (Earley, 2001), (Nurim & Harjanto, 2015), (Hirst & Luckett, 1992), (Borthick, Curtis, & Sriram, 2006), and (Lukviarman, 2016). Correspondingly, perfect corporate governance can strengthen intra-company controls and reduce opportunistic behavior and reduce information asymmetry. It has a positive effect on the high-quality disclosure of information (Li & Qi, 2008). Embark from those situations, the purpose of this study is to test the role of the human capital of an independent commissioner by its' mediating and moderating role testing in the relationship between independent commissioner's existence and credit performance of Indonesian Rural Bank. So, the detailed objectives of this research are (1) to test that the independent commissioner's existence has a significant effect on the credit performance of Indonesian Rural Bank; (2) to test that the human capital of independent commissioner has a significant effect on the credit performance of Indonesian Rural Bank; and (3) to test that the human capital of independent commissioner moderates the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and the credit performance of Indonesian Rural Bank.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Independent Commissioner is a member of the Board of Commissioners who does not have financial, management, share ownership, and or family relationships with other members of the Board of Commissioners, Board of Directors, and/or controlling shareholder or other relationship that can affect his ability to act independently (OJK, 2015). Independent commissioners have a significant positive relationship with ROA and company stock returns in general (Rostami et al., 2015). These results are supported by (Manzaneque, Priego, & Merino, 2016; Nisasmara & Musdholifah, 2016; Nurim, Sunardi, & Raharti, 2017) others financial performances. The formulation of the financial performance of banking is usually done by using Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Operating Expense compared to Operating Income Ratio (OEIOI), Non-Performing Loans (NPL), and other financial ratio analyses (Chabachib, Yudha, Hersugondo, Pamungkas, & Udin, 2019; Cochran & Wood, 1984; Wu & Shen, 2013). Relating to the various measures of banking financial performance, the authors use the measurement of credit performance of banking following the characteristics of the rural bank (microfinance). It is based on the ratio of credit performance of Non-Performing Loans (NPL); related to BPR credit risk because the loans provided usually have small guarantees (Armendariz & Morduch, 2005). In the term of credit performance, the existence of independent commissioner at Indonesian Rural Bank has a positive relationship with its credit performance (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). Thus, the first hypothesis of this study is:

H1: The independent commissioner's existence has a significant effect on the credit performance

In the others, previous studies (Agrawal & Knoeber, 1996; Bhagat & Black, 2001; Drakos & Bekiris, 2010; Klein, 1998; Yermack, 1996) found that there was no significant relationship between the presence of independent commissioner and firm performance. The mixed findings suggest further research is needed. Previous studies have not considered corporate governance's mediating and moderating effect (Hsu et al., 2012; Kurnia, Darlis, & Putra, 2020). Most of the research investigating the relationship between corporate governance and company performance is direct without a moderator and mediator (Hersugondo & Udin, 2019; Khajar, Hersugondo, & Udin, 2018; Sunarto, Widjaja, & Oktaviani, 2021; Wahidahwati & Ardini, 2021).

According to (Basyith, 2016), some companies choose commissioners based on good relations or friendship, so its existence does not cause a positive and significant impact on the performance or value of the company. In the context of companies in Indonesia, also supported by Novia & Lukviarman (2006), there is a positive indication of increased corporate compliance in Indonesia to improve board governance structures but allegedly increased compliance due to the company's obligation to comply with regulations and avoid sanctions. The success of the mechanism for implementing the governance of the board of commissioners concerning its duties ensures that the Indonesian Rural Bank's board carries out good governance. It is necessary to have an appropriate judgment in the assessment. In some studies in the context of behavioral accounting have revealed the vital role of knowledge on the accuracy of judgment, such as Bonner & Lewis (1990), Earley (2001), Nurim & Harjanto (2015). Knowledge enhances the cognitive appropriateness of the judgments with his assignments, so judgment is more accurate. It is also supported by Hirst et al. (1999) and Borthick et al. (2006), which states that the performance and accuracy of a judgment are influenced by appropriate knowledge and are obtained formally at the proper level as well. In terms of the board of commissioners as a mechanism for internal governance, it is essential to note the background of experience and expertise possessed by the board of commissioners; the composition and the right combination will have a positive impact on the company's performance through optimizing the strategic role of the board of commissioners (Lukviarman, 2016). Thus, commissioner knowledge will have a positive effect on the company's financial performance. OJK (2016) also states that Indonesian Rural Banks also experienced problems in the lack of human resources expertise of Indonesian Rural Bank, including its human capital of independent commissioner.

Human capital leads to higher business performance (Sriviboon, 2021). Therefore, the author attempts to consider the human capital of the independent commissioner element that may affect the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. The author also attempts to consider the human capital of an independent commissioner as an element that may affect the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank using Baron and Kenny's Model (Baron & Kenny, 1986). Thus, the second and third hypothesis of this study is:

H2: The human capital of independent commissioner has a significant effect on the credit performance

H3: The human capital of independent commissioner moderates the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and credit performance

RESEARCH METHOD

The Research Data and Sample

According to the objectives, the steps in this study are:

1. The secondary data in the form of annual financial statements and information related to this research in 2016 from selected Indonesian Rural Bank samples taken from the BI website (www.bi.go.id) and or OJK website (www.ojk.go.id) and the corresponding Indonesian Rural Bank's website.
2. The collected secondary data will be processed and analyzed using multiple cross-sectional steps linear regressions using SPSS statistic software, and the results will also be described in depth.

Samples of this study are taken using a purposive sampling method of the Rural Banks population in Indonesia. The sample of this study is the Rural Banks in Central Java and the Special Region of Yogyakarta Provinces which have higher financial performance than the national average. Determination of the sample using the purposive sampling method is done to obtain the sample that meets the criteria with unique specifications according to the problems. The criteria are:

1. Indonesian Rural Banks with a core capital of less than IDR 50 billion
2. The Indonesian Rural Bank is still in operation until the end of June 2016
3. The Indonesian Rural Bank publishes its annual financial statements and other information in June of 2016 on the website of Bank Indonesia (BI) and the Indonesian Financial Services Authority (OJK)
4. The Indonesian Rural Bank published the information related to the data which is needed in this research on the respective Indonesian Rural Bank website.

The Definition of Research Variables and Models

Based on the previous studies and the development of research hypotheses, the authors derived dependent variables, independent variables, and control variables from this study. The dependent variable of this research is credit performance which is more reflected explicitly by a proxy of Indonesian Rural Bank's Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). Credit performance ratio, which is namely Non-Performing Loans (NPL); related to BPR credit risk because the credit provided usually has little collateral (Chatterjee, Sarangi, Armendáriz, & Morduch, 2006) and (Cochran & Wood, 1984; Wu & Shen, 2013; OJK, 2015). A non-performing loan (NPL) is a loan in which the borrower is in default and has not paid the monthly principal and interest recurring payment for a specified period (usually bank uses which are due for more than

90 days). In this study, the use of the NPL ratio as the dependent variable is calculated using the formula: (non-performing loan/total loan) X 100%.

The independent variable of hypothesis 1 of this study is The independent Indonesian Rural Bank Commissioner's Existence variable. It is indicated by the value 0 if there is no independent commissioner in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank. The value of 1 if there is one independent commissioner in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank. The value 2 if there are two independent commissioners in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018).

The dependent variable of this hypothesis 2 research is credit performance, the same as hypothesis 1 as Indonesian Rural Bank's Non-Performing Loans (NPLs). The independent variable of hypothesis 2 of this study is the human capital of the independent commissioner Score. The human capital of the independent commissioner Score is indicated by its education suitability in terms of the minimum education level of S1 from majoring in economics or business of the commissioner in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). This is also applied as moderating variables and indicated by 1 if the commissioner of the respective Indonesian Rural Bank has education level under S1 (Bachelor); 2 if the commissioner in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank has a minimum education level of S1 from non-economic or business majors; and 3 if the commissioner in the respective Indonesian Rural Bank has a minimum education level of S1 from majoring in economics or business (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018).

Based on the research variables that have been determined, then the secondary data related to these research variables that have been collected will be processed and analyzed by cross-sectional regression using statistic software with a significance level of 5%. Data processing and analysis will be done by the model for hypothesis 1 until hypothesis 3 as follows:

$$H1: NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_N + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$$

$$H2: NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_HC + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$$

$$H3: NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_N + b2In.Com._RB_HC + b3In.Com._RB_N * In.Com._HC_Ed + b4Log.T.As_RB + e$$

Note:

1. *Dependent Variable; NPL_RB = Non-Performing Loans of Indonesian Rural Bank*
2. *Independent Variable; In.Com._RB_N = Number of Indonesian Rural Bank's Independent Commissioner*
3. *Moderating Variable; In.Com._RB_HC = Total Score of the Human Capital of Indonesian Rural Bank's Independent Commissioner*
4. *Control Variables; Log.T.As_RB = Log of Indonesian Rural Bank's Total Assets*

Figure 1: Main Model of the Study (Hypothesis 3)

RESEARCH RESULTS

In this research, to test the research hypothesis, 177 samples of Indonesian rural banks are tested. Those samples are meet the purposive sampling criteria mention in the previous section. The descriptive statistics of the sample data is depicted in the table below:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Sample Data

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev.
In.Com._RB_N	177	0	3	1.36	.821
In.Com._RB_HC	177	0	8	3.00	2.231
Log.T.As_RB	177	6.939	8.873	7.934	.499
In.Com._RB_N * In.Com._RB_HC	177	0	24	5.63	5.492
NPL_RB	177	0	17	4.50	3.173
Valid N (listwise)	177				

Hypothesis 1 Testing Result

For hypothesis 1 testing, the minimum Number of Independent Commissioner is 0, the maximum is 3, with a mean and standard deviation of 1.36 and 0.821. For Non-Performing Loans, the minimal number is 0.4269, and the maximal number is 17.4802 with a mean of 4.50 and standard deviation of 3.173.

The coefficient of R square is 15.2%. The Number of Independent Commissioner as controlled by Log Total Assets affects Non-Performing Loans by 15.2%. It also means that the other variables that do not include in the model affect Non-Performing Loans about 84.8%.

The linear regression of the Number of Independent Commissioner as the independent variable and Non-Performing Loans as a dependent variable has a significant level of 0.000 with the coefficient of regression of – 1.574. The linear regression of Log Total Assets as a control variable and Non-Performing Loans as a dependent variable has a significant level of 0.534 with the coefficient of regression of 0.302.

Table 2: ANOVA of Hypothesis 1 Testing

Model	H1: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_N + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$		
	Regression	Residual	Total
Sum of Squares	269.837	1.501.873	1.771.710
Df	2	174	176
Mean Square	134.918	8.631	
F	15.631		
Sig.	.000 ^b		

a. Dependent Variable: NPL_RB

b. Predictors: (Constant), In.Com._RB_N, Log.T.As_RB

Table 3: Coefficients of Hypothesis 1 Testing

Model	H1: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_N + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$			
		(Constant)	In.Com._RB_N	Log.T.As_RB
Independent Variables				
Dependent Variable	NPL_RB			
Unstandardized Coefficients	B	4.236	-1.574	.302
	Std. Error	3.717	.296	.486
Standardized Coefficients	Beta		-.407	.048
T		1.140	-5.327	.622
Sig.		.256	.000	.534
R Square	.152			
Std. Error of the Estimate	2.938			

Hypothesis 2 Testing Result

For hypothesis 2 testing, the minimum human capital of independent commissioner score is 0, the maximum is 8, with a mean and standard deviation of 3 and 2.231. For Non-Performing Loans, the minimal number is 0.4269, and the maximal number is 17.4802 with a mean of 4.50 and standard deviation of 3.173.

The coefficient of R square is 15.6%. It means that the variable of the human capital of independent commissioner score as controlled by Log Total Assets affects Non-Performing Loans by 15.6%. It also means that the other variables that do not include in the model affect Non-Performing Loans about 84.4%.

The linear regression of the human capital of independent commissioner score as the independent variable and Non-Performing Loans as a dependent variable has a significant level of 0.000 with the coefficient of regression of – 0.573. The linear regression of Log Total Assets as a control variable and Non-Performing Loans as a dependent variable has a significant level of 0.736 with the coefficient of regression of 0.160.

Table 4: ANOVA of Hypothesis 2 Testing

Model	H2: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com._RB_HC + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$		
	Regression	Residual	Total
Sum of Squares	275.774	1.495.936	1.771.710
df	2	174	176
Mean Square	137.887	8.597	
F	16.038		
Sig.	.000 ^b		

a. Dependent Variable: NPL_RB

b. Predictors: (Constant), In.Com._RB_HC, Log.T.As_RB

Table 5: Coefficients of Hypothesis 2 Testing

Model		H2: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com_RB_HC + b2Log.T.As_RB + e$		
Independent Variables		(Constant)	In.Com._RB_HC	Log.T.As_RB
Dependent Variable	NPL_RB			
Unstandardized Coefficients	B	4.951	-.573	.160
	Std. Error	3.666	.106	.474
Standardized Coefficients	Beta		-.403	.025
t		1.350	-5.402	.338
Sig.		.179	.000	.736
R Square	.156			
Std. Error of the Estimate	2.932			

Hypothesis 3 Testing Result

The coefficient of the R square is 18.7%. The variable of Number of Independent Commissioner after controlled by human capital of independent commissioner score as moderating variable and interaction variable of Number of Independent Commissioner and human capital of independent commissioner score affects Non-Performing Loans by 18.7%. It also means that the other variables that do not include in the model affect Non-Performing Loans about 81.3%. Here, the coefficient of R square increase by 3.5% (from 15.2% to 18.7%).

The linear regression of the Number of Independent Commissioner as the main independent variable and Non-Performing Loans as a dependent variable has a significant level of 0.338 with the coefficient of regression of - 0.573 after controlled by human capital of independent commissioner score as moderating variable and interaction variable of Number of Independent Commissioner and human capital of independent commissioner score. On the other hand, the linear regression of human capital of independent commissioner score as moderating variable and Non-Performing Loans as an independent variable has a significant level of 0.573 with the coefficient of regression of 0.180. Meanwhile, the linear regression of the interaction variable of Number of Independent Commissioner and human capital of independent commissioner score and Non-Performing Loans as an independent variable has a significant level of 0.048 with the coefficient of regression of - 0.249.

Table 6: ANOVA of Hypothesis 3 Testing

Model	H3: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com_RB_N + b2In.Com_RB_HC + b3In.Com_RB_N * In.Com_HC_Ed + b4Log.T.As_RB + e$		
	Regression	Residual	Total
Sum of Squares	331.776	1.439.934	1.771.710
Df	4	172	176
Mean Square	82.944	8.372	
F	9.908		
Sig.	.000b		

a. Dependent Variable: NPL_RB

b. Predictors: (Constant), In.Com._RB_N, In.Com._RB_HC, In.Com._RB_N * In.Com._HC_Ed, Log.T.As_RB

Table 7: Coefficients of Hypothesis 3 Testing

Model		H3: $NPL_RB = a + b1In.Com_RB_N + b2In.Com_RB_HC + b3In.Com_RB_N * In.Com_HC_Ed + b4Log.T.As_RB + e$				
Independent Variables		(Constant)	In.Com._RB_N	In.Com._RB_HC	In.Com._RB_N * In.Com._HC_Ed	Log.T.As_RB
Dependent Variable	NPL_RB					
Unstandardized Coefficients	B	2.698	-.596	.206	-.263	.438
	Std. Error	3.721	.536	.320	.126	.482
Standardized Coefficients	Beta		-.154	.145	-.456	.069
t		.725	-1.112	.643	-2.084	.908

Sig.		.469	.268	.521	.039	.365
R Square	.187					
Std. Error of the Estimate	2.893					

DISCUSSION

The testing result shows that H1 is accepted. From the linear regression, as shown by the table the significant level of 0.000 or it is < 0.05 with the coefficient of regression of $- 1.574$. It means that the Number of Independent Commissioner of Indonesian Rural Bank has a negative impact on Non-Performing Loans of Indonesian Rural Banks (positive for credit performance). Every additional Number of Independent Commissioner will affect the lower in Non-Performing Loans by 1.574 or increase the credit performance by 1.574. This result supports the previous research of Nisasmara and Musdholifa (2016), Manzaneque et al. (2016), Nurim et al. (2016), and (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). It can be explained that the Indonesian Rural Bank that has an independent commissioner has better credit performance than that which does not or even has much better credit performance for those that have a more independent commissioner.

The testing result shows that H2 is accepted. Based on the linear regression, as shown by the table, the significant level of 0.000 or it is < 0.05 with the coefficient of regression of $- 0.573$. It means that the human capital of an independent commissioner has a negative impact on Non-Performing Loans of Indonesian Rural Bank (positive/good for credit performance). Every additional level of The Appropriateness of Expertise of Independent Commissioner will affect the lower Non-Performing Loans by 0.573 or increase the credit performance by 0.573. This result supports the previous research of Bonner and Walker (1994), Earley (2001 and 2003), Nurim and Harjanto (2015), Hirst et al. (1999), Borthick et al. (2006), Lukviarman (2016), and (Harjanto & Rahmawati, 2018). It can be explained that the Indonesian Rural Bank that has an independent commissioner who has appropriate business education has better credit performance than those that do not. Moreover, it has much better credit performance for an independent commissioner who has a higher level of appropriate business education.

The testing result shows that H3 is accepted. From the linear regression of the human capital of independent commissioner and Non-Performing Loans, as demonstrated by the table, the significant level of 0.573 or it is > 0.05 (not significant) with the coefficient of regression of 0.180. Meanwhile, the linear regression of the interaction variable of Number of Independent Commissioner and human capital of independent commissioner score and Non-Performing Loans, as shown by the table, is the significant level of 0.048 or < 0.05 (significant) the coefficient of regression of $- 0.249$. So, it is proven that the human capital of independent commissioner moderates the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. The coefficient of R square increase by 3.5% (from 15.2% to 18.7%). It means that the human capital of the independent commissioner score strengthens the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. That interaction has a negative impact on Non-Performing Loans of Indonesian Rural Bank (positive for credit performance). Every additional level of that interaction will affect the lower in Non-Performing Loans by 0.249 or increase the credit performance by 0.249. The human capital of an independent commissioner should support the existence of an independent commissioner as a mechanism for the internal governance mechanism of Indonesian Rural Banks with a core capital of less than IDR 50 billion.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the human capital of independent commissioner moderates the effect of the independent commissioner's existence on the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. Hopefully, this research results will give empirical evidence and a comprehensive understanding to the academicians and public researchers that the human capital of an independent commissioner has a vital role in the relationship between the independent commissioner's existence and the credit performance of the Indonesian Rural Bank. Hopefully, the result will be the proposal to OJK to revise the Regulation of the Indonesian Financial Services Authority number 4/POJK.03/2015. It relates to the compulsory existence of an independent commissioner as one mechanism of internal governance of Indonesian Rural Banks with core capital that less than IDR 50 billion and should be supported by the human capital of an independent commissioner. That internal governance mechanism is crucial to ensure the effective implementation of Indonesian Rural Bank's governance.

Limitation of Research

This research is conducted by testing the effect of independent commissioner's existence on credit performance by examining the moderating role of the human capital of independent commissioners of the Indonesian Rural Bank using the purposive sampling method. The Indonesian Rural Banks, which do not meet

the criteria with unique specifications according to the problems that occur, cannot serve the appropriate secondary data and cannot be involved in this research as the sample data. The number of those Indonesian Rural Bank is more extensive than these research samples.

Future Research Direction

Future research can combine secondary and primary data (by survey and interview) to dig more deeply into Indonesian Rural Bank's independent commissioner to support that internal governance mechanism. By combining these collection data methods, the number of Indonesian Rural Bank can be involved for the study sample will also be much bigger, so the supporting data for better research results can also be achieved. That is very important to ensure the effective implementation of Indonesian Rural Bank's governance.

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